

METHODOLOGY FOR SOLVING STUDENTS' PROBLEMS OF CREATIVE AND CRITICAL THINKING BASED ON COGNITIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES.

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Abstract. *This article provides detailed information on the methodology for solving students' problems of creative and critical thinking based on cognitive learning technologies, as well as the methods that should be applied in modern pedagogy.*

Keywords: *Flexible thinking, alternative thinking, non-standard thinking, logical reasoning, metacognitive strategies, reflection, problem-based learning, divergent thinking, humanitarian approaches, Socratic conversation, independent research, visual and interactive technologies.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada kognitiv ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida o'quvchilarning ijodiy va tanqidiy fikrlashdagi muammolarini hal etish metodikasi hamda bugungi zamonaviy pedagogikada qo'llanilishi lozim bo'lgan metodlar haqida batafsil ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Fleksibil tafakkur, alternativ fikrlash, nostandart fikrlash, Mantiqiy asoslash, metakognitiv strategiyalar, refleksiya, muammoli ta'lim, divergent fikrlash, gumanitar yondashuvlar, Sokratik suhbat, mustaqil izlanish, vizual va interfaol texnologiyalar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена подробная информация о методике решения проблем творческого и критического мышления учащихся на основе когнитивных образовательных технологий, а также о методах, которые необходимо использовать в современной педагогике.*

Ключевые слова: *Флексибельное мышление, альтернативное мышление, нестандартное мышление, логическое обоснование, метакогнитивные стратегии, рефлексия, проблемное обучение, дивергентное мышление, гуманитарные подходы, сократическая беседа, самостоятельный поиск, визуальные и интерактивные технологии.*

Introduction. In today's rapidly changing world, the formation of students' creative and critical thinking skills has become one of the most important tasks of education. Traditional teaching methods are often based on memorization of knowledge, which is insufficiently effective in developing students' independent thinking, problem-solving, and innovative approaches. Why is this issue important? Global education systems are adapting to the demands of today's labor market. Modern employers need specialists who can think creatively, solve problems, and are ready to innovate. In conditions of excessive information, students must have the ability to think critically. Identifying false information, comparing information from different sources, and making informed decisions are important skills. In the era of science, technology, and innovation, the creative approach of students allows them to create new ideas, start-ups, and develop projects that benefit society. Cognitive learning technologies are based on the application of methods and tools aimed at developing brain activity and thinking processes. These technologies contribute to the formation of students' abilities such as analyzing and processing information, independently solving problems, conducting research and applying a

creative approach, substantiating and critically evaluating their opinions, and developing flexible thinking. Solving problems in the creative and critical thinking of students based on cognitive educational technologies is not only the main direction of the modern education system, but also an important condition for social and economic development. In this regard, the introduction of new methods by educational institutions and teachers is of great importance.

Literature review. Scientists such as R.Jacobson [1], P.A.Facione, M.Lipman, as well as domestic scientists and researchers such as S.T.Kalekeeva [2], [3], S.Toshtemirova, S.Akhmadov, B.Zhuraboev [4] worked on the methodology for solving students' problems of creative and critical thinking based on cognitive educational technologies.

Main Part. Cognitive educational technologies are an effective tool for the development of students' creative thinking and the formation of problem-solving skills. These technologies contribute to the development of innovative approaches by increasing intellectual activity in the learning process, stimulating independent thinking, and analyzing problem situations. Solving creative problems based on cognitive learning technologies includes the following stages:

1. Understanding and analyzing the problem. Students should understand the essence of the problem and analyze it in separate parts. Method: “Analytical questions”, “Brainstorming”, SWOT analysis.

2. Data collection and processing. Students accumulate the necessary knowledge on the topic and connect it with existing knowledge. Method: “Cluster”, “Venn diagram”, “Conceptual map”.

3. Creating ideas and developing alternative solutions. Students develop creative approaches through various methods. Method: TRIZ, SCAMPER, Sinextics, “Double Scale” method.

4. Selection and justification of the most effective solution. Students evaluate the developed solutions and choose the most effective one. Method: “Pluses and Minuses”, “6 De Bonos Hats”, “Matrix Evaluation”.

5. Application of the solution and analysis of the results. The chosen solution is tested in practice, and the results are evaluated. Method: “Project work”, “Role-playing”, “Reflection and discussion”.

For the development of creative thinking, metacognitive strategies are used, i.e., students' awareness and management of their thinking processes (for example, “Targeted Learning Diary”), problem-based learning, i.e., providing students with the opportunity to solve problems independently, methods of analogy and association, i.e., creating new ideas based on existing knowledge, digital technologies, i.e., artificial intelligence, virtual laboratories, simulations, and interactive tools.

One of the most important factors in solving the problems of students' creative and critical thinking is the development of “Flexible thinking” in them. Flexible thinking (from the Latin *flexibilis* - flexible, adaptable) is a person's ability to adapt their thinking process to changing conditions. In other words, a person with flexible thinking can approach different problems from different points of view, consider alternative solutions, and quickly adapt to innovations. This helps us cope with uncertainty, solve problems, adapt to changes, and incorporate new information into our plans and ideas.¹ Flexible thinking is also a key aspect of self-regulation and managing big emotions. Flexible thinking has the following characteristics:

¹ R.Jacobson “Helping kids with flexible thinking”. The official website of the Child Mind Institute, childmind.org. March 8, 2024.

- Flexibility - the ability to quickly adapt to new situations.

Alternative thinking is finding several ways to solve one problem. The study of alternative ideas is an important part of the logical thinking process, which encourages a person to look at a particular problem from different angles. This approach involves considering different opinions on a problem or issue, evaluating them, and studying the advantages and disadvantages of each.²

- Testing new approaches - not getting bogged down in old methods and accepting innovations.

- Creative approach to problems - creation of innovative ideas through non-standard thinking. Non-standard thinking is the ability of a person to create new ideas, to deviate from the traditional scheme of thinking and make unique, original decisions.³

Applying existing knowledge to new situations - the ability to apply what has been learned in various fields.

Flexible thinking is the key to students' success, as it makes a person adaptable, creative, and open to innovation.

Also, various problems arise in the process of forming critical thinking in students. These problems need to be deeply analyzed.

Firstly, the inability to independently formulate an opinion, that is, excessive trust in ready-made ideas, the inability to doubt them, difficulty in forming one's own independent point of view.

Secondly, difficulties in understanding logical connections, that is, the inability to see the connection between arguments and conclusions, a lack of a deep understanding of cause-and-effect relationships. Logical reasoning is the ability to justify an opinion or conclusion, indicate the reasons for it, and explain its correctness. With the help of logical reasoning, a person reinforces their opinion, shows why it is correct, and tries to convince others of their opinion. This ability helps a person to draw accurate conclusions based on facts and approach them objectively in the process of thinking.⁴

Thirdly, the weakness of creative thinking, that is, the lack of a tendency to look at problems from different angles, not trying to solve problems through new approaches.

Fourthly, the weakness in identifying and discussing the problem, that is, the difficulty of recognizing the problem in a given situation and formulating it clearly, making a superficial conclusion without a deep study of the problem.

Fifthly, low ability to verify and filter information, that is, relying on unreliable sources, difficulty in determining whether the data is true or false.

A methodology for solving students' problems of creative and critical thinking based on cognitive learning technologies is developed for the formation of the ability to solve the above-mentioned problems. It will be organized in integration with problem-based learning, active learning methods, techniques that stimulate intellectual development, and modern digital technologies.

² S.T.Kalekeeva “Concepts of logical thinking and factors of their development” VI Traditional international scientific and practical conference “Professional development of the personality of the xxi century in the system of continuous education: Problems and ways of their solution”. December 3-4, 2024. Page 283.

³ S.Toshtemirova, S.Akhmadov, B.Zhuraboev. “Nonstandard thinking skills features of improvement”. “Pedagogical Education Cluster: Problems and Solutions” proceedings of the international conference. Page 1543

⁴ S.T.Kalekeeva “Concepts of logical thinking and factors of their development” VI Traditional international scientific and practical conference “Professional development of the personality of the xxi century in the system of continuous education: Problems and ways of their solution”. December 3-4, 2024. Pages 283-284.

These technologies include the following main areas:

1. Metacognitive strategies. For example: reflection - students learn to analyze their knowledge and self-assess. Self-regulated learning - students learn to plan, control, and evaluate their learning processes.

2. Problem-Based Learning (PBL). Problem-based approach - acquiring knowledge through real-life situations or problems.

3. Research-Based Learning (Inquiry-Based Learning). Independent research - students conduct research by asking questions themselves. Experiment and experience - consolidation of theoretical knowledge through practical research.

4. Humanitarian approaches. Brain-Based Learning - the application of teaching methods corresponding to the brain activity of students.

5. Visual and interactive technologies. For example: Graphic organizers, digital technologies - artificial intelligence, educational programs, virtual and augmented reality (VR, AR).

6. Development of critical and creative thinking. Divergent thinking is finding multiple solutions to a single problem. Socratic conversation - directing to deep thinking through questions.

These technologies serve to eliminate problems in the process of creative and critical thinking of students, develop their thinking abilities, and form their skills of independent learning and innovation.

Conclusion. Cognitive learning technologies, based on the principles of the functioning of the human mind, contribute to the effective assimilation of knowledge, the development of independent thinking and problem-solving skills. Their effectiveness in creative and critical thinking is manifested in the following:

- Through creative thinking, it helps to approach problems in a new way, promote innovative ideas, and find non-standard solutions.

- Through problem-based learning, it involves students in the process of solving real problems and helps them find unique, creative solutions.

- Develops a creative approach to understanding and controlling one's thinking process through metacognitive strategies.

- Allows modeling creative problems in a virtual environment through didactic games and simulations or through practical exercises.

Cognitive learning technologies are an important tool for the development of creative and critical thinking. Through them, students will have the opportunity to manage their thinking processes, solve problems using innovative approaches, and develop independent thinking skills. Therefore, CTT serves as an important methodological basis in the modern educational process.

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